

A Magnetic Study of the Colour Changes in Cobalt Chloride.

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The well-known and striking colour changes red \rightleftharpoons blue of cobalt chloride solutions have led to considerable controversy. Numerous early investigators (Babo, *Jahresber.*, 1857, 72; Schiff, *ibid.*, 1859, 52; Gladstone, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1858, 10, 79; 1859, 11, 36; Russell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1881, 32, 253; Hartley, *Sci. Proc. Roy. Dubl. Soc.*, 1900, ii, 7, 253; etc.) have endeavoured to explain the colour changes entirely in terms of varying hydration of the cobalt chloride. The explanations of the colour phenomena by Engel (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1891, iii, 6, 230) on the concept of double salts in solution and by tions Ostwald from single ionic standpoint are both untenable.

Donnan and Bassett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 939) explained the colour changes on the basis of some such equilibrium as

Hartley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 401) considered that $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CoCl_2 were formed on heating aqueous solutions of cobalt chloride. Lewis (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1905, 52, 224), Jones and Bassett (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1905, 52, 231) and Hulbert, Hutchinson and Jones (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, 21, 150) have also explained the colour changes entirely in terms of hydration theory.

Moore (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1906, 58, 641) from his spectroscopic measurements considers the existence of complex ions very probable. Brown (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1912, 32, 50) on the other hand, from his measurements on absorption of light by cobalt chloride solutions favours the hydration theory.

Denham (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1909, 65, 641) from measurements of transport numbers concluded that "auto-complexes" were present in solutions of cobalt bromide.

Gróh (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 136, 305) from molecular extinction coefficients supports the assumption of an equilibrium

the blue colour of the solutions being due to the complex ion CoCl''_4 . Gr6h and Schmid (*ibid.*, 1927, **162**, 321) came to the same conclusion from observations on the solubility of lithium chloride in acetone solutions of cobalt chloride.

Kotschubei (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **46**, 1055) studied the water carried by the ions by Nernst's method, using phenols as the indicator. He found that the hydration of the cobalt ion and of undissociated cobalt molecules diminished with increase of concentration and rise of temperature, and considered that the change was probably from $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6''$ to $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4''$ and $\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{c} (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \\ \text{Cl}_2 \end{array} \right]$ and not to CoCl''_4 .

Hill and Howell (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, *vi*, **48**, 833) suggested that whether cobalt compounds are red or blue depends upon the state of co-ordination of the cobalt atom; if this is surrounded by six other groups or atoms, a red colour results, while if there are only four groups or atoms, the colour is blue.

Bassett and Croucher (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1784) fail to reconcile this view with the electrical evidence as to the nature of the red and blue solutions. They conclude that colour is independent of the state of co-ordination.

It is evident from the above resumé of the subject that the theory of the constitution of cobalt salts in solution is far from satisfactory. The magnetic properties of the salts in solution would naturally suggest themselves to investigators as likely studies which would shed a flood of light on the subject.

The magnetic behaviour of cobalt salts in solution is in itself quite complicated. With concentration of the chloride ranging from 0.5 to 0.005 g. mols per litre, Trumpler and Cabrera (*J. Phys. Radium*, 1922, *vi*, **3**, 443), obtained values for p lying between 24.53 and 24.59. With the addition of hydrochloric acid, Cabrera (*loc. cit.*) found that the equilibrium between the different ionic carriers was displaced in a direction which suggested that there may also be carrier of moment less than 23 Weiss magnetons.

Chatillon (*Ann. Physique*, 1928, **9**, 187), found for aqueous solutions of CoCl_2 , CoSO_4 and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, a value of 25.02 for the Weiss magneton number. In amyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol cobalt chloride gave the value of 23 for p , the Weiss magneton number and the aqueous solutions of CoCl_2 diluted with hydrochloric acid gave results depending on the concentration of the acid. It appears that similar

solutions do not always give the same results ; the temperature variation is linear only over a limited range and magneton numbers 22, 23, 24, 25 and 26 were found.

From the above it is clear that the magnetic behaviour of the cobalt salts in solution is very complicated. In this paper we have determined

(a) The value of p , the Weiss magneton number, for the cobalt salts in aqueous solutions, and

(b) The variation of p , with concentration for various hydrates of cobalt chloride in different solvents.

From these and from the results of other investigations, we have attempted to clarify our views regarding the constitution of cobalt salts in solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus employed during this investigation was in principle similar to Bauer and Piccard's U-tube type and is fully described in a previous paper (Bhatnagar, Mathur and Mal, *Phil. Mag.*, 1930, vii, 10, 101) from this laboratory.

As in the original method of Bauer and Piccard (*J. Phys. Radium*, 1920, vi, 1, 97) the meniscus, after cutting on the field, could be brought back to the initial position by raising or lowering the reservoir and the rise or fall read on a fine micrometer. These readings were checked with those taken directly on a travelling microscope.

Now, according to the well-known expression, the specific mass susceptibility is given by

$$\chi = \frac{2\theta g}{H^2} + \chi_o \frac{\rho_o}{\rho}$$

where χ_o = specific susceptibility of air ($21 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-6}$),

ρ_o = density of air at the given temperature and pressure,

ρ = density of substance under investigation,

θ = rise or fall of the meniscus.

The apparatus was standardised with respect to water ($\chi = -7 \cdot 25 \times 10^{-7}$).

Salts.

Pure specimens of Kahlbaum's were taken and their purity determined by ordinary methods of chemical analysis.

From the mass susceptibilities of the salt solutions as calculated from the expression given above, the volume susceptibilities were calculated. The mass susceptibility of the salt is given by the expression :

$$\chi_{\text{salt}}^m = \frac{\chi_{\text{solution}}^v - \chi_{\text{air}}^v - \left(\chi_{\text{solvent}}^m \times \frac{W_{\text{solvent}}}{1000} \right)}{\frac{W_{\text{solute}}}{1000}} \quad \text{and } \chi_M,$$

the gram molecular susceptibility is given by $\chi_M = \chi_{\text{salt}}^m \times M$. wt.

The Curie constant C_M was calculated from $C_M = \chi_M \cdot T$ where T is the absolute temperature. The Weiss relation $C_M = \chi_M (T - \theta)$ could not be employed as the range of temperatures investigated was not large enough to extrapolate the value of θ .

Then p , the number of Weiss magnetons is given by $p = 14.07 \sqrt{C_M}$.

TABLE I.

Condition in which Co ion is placed.	Moments in magnetons.	Reference.
Aqueous solution of		
Co(NO ₃) ₂	25.05	Present work
	25.02	Chatillon (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
CoCl ₂	25.04	Present work
	25.05	Chatillon
CoSO ₄	25.04	Chatillon
CoCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O (solid)	25.03	Chatillon
CoCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O (solid)	25.02	Present work
Anhydrous CoCl ₂	24.96	Theodorides (<i>J. Phys. Radium</i> , 1922, vi, 3, 1)
Anhydrous CoSO ₄	25.06	Do
	24.95	
CoSO ₄ calcined at temperature lower than 400°.	25.07	Chatillon
CoSO ₄ calcined at dull red heat.	25.98	Miss Serres (<i>Compt. rend.</i> , 1926, 181, 714)
	25.98	Chatillon

TABLE II.

Condition in which Co ion is placed.	Moments in magnetons.	Reference.
Solutions of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ethyl alcohol		
12.519 g. per 100 g.	22.48	
4.459 " " " "	22.28	Present work
CoCl_2 in ethyl alcohol	23.00	Chatillon
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methyl alcohol		
10.86 g. per 100 g.	23.00	
8.55 " " " "	22.75	Present work
4.568 " " " "	24.42	
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methyl alcohol	23.02	Present work
Solutions of CoCl_2 in amyl alcohol		
	23.04	Chatillon
	23.01	Present work
Solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a mixture of ethyl and amyl alcohol	23.08	Present work
CoCl_2 crystallised in absolute alcohol	26.02	Chatillon

TABLE III.

Condition in which Co ion is placed.	Moments in magnetons.	Reference.
Solutions of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixed with HCl	25.07	
	23.47	
Varying concentrations of HCl	23.52	Chatillon
	23.46	
	22.03	
	21.97	
Solution of CoCl_2 in concentrated sulphuric acid	25.66	Foex (<i>Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.</i> , 1929, 55, 97)

Summary and Discussion of Results.

Table I confirms the conclusions of Chatillon that in all aqueous solutions of cobalt salts, the value of the Weiss magneton number is 25. From a comparison of this value to the values of p , the Weiss magneton, found by other investigators for different salts of cobalt in the solid state, it appears that the normal value for the red Co^{++} ion is 25.

Table II gives the values of the Weiss magneton for solutions of different hydrates of cobalt chloride in ethyl, methyl and amyl alcohols. It is interesting to note that when $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is dissolved in ethyl alcohol, the value of p varies between 22 and 23 according to the concentration of the solution and it never reaches as high as 25 which is the established normal value for aqueous solu-

tions. Similar results have been obtained in methyl alcohol and amyl alcohol solutions.

If the paramagnetic ions in solution remain all of one kind, the value of p shall also remain constant. But if ions characterised by different Weiss magneton values p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n are present, then the value of p is given by

$$p^2 = \frac{1}{n} (n_1 p_1^2 + n_2 p_2^2 + \dots)$$

where n_1, n_2, \dots give the relative number of ions of Weiss magneton values p_1, p_2, \dots and $n = n_1 + n_2, \dots$. And as variations in concentrations of a solution change the relative values of n_1, n_2, \dots , a variation in the values of p with concentration of the solution must take place. The fact that the alcoholic solutions of cobalt salts have colours varying from blue-violet to pink, would suggest the presence of different ionic carriers, which would result in variation of p with concentration. We find from our results that the value of p does change with concentration.

When we examine these results with those obtained by Chatillon for $\text{CoCl}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in HCl solutions we are immediately struck by the remarkable fact that in all these cases the value of p falls from 25 to a figure between 22 and 24. This fall in the value of p from 25 to somewhere between 22 and 24 is not due to the production of the anhydrous CoCl_2 as suggested by Lewis (*loc. cit.*), Jones and Bassett (*loc. cit.*) or to $\text{CoCl}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as suggested by Hartley (*loc. cit.*), as the value of p for both these salts is approximately 25, the usual value for cobalt salts. The addition of HCl will result in formation of ions of the $(\text{CoCl}_3)'$ and $(\text{CoCl}_4)''$ type and it is clear that the addition of Cl' to the CoCl_2 will have the effect of bringing down the value of p , as happens to be the case.

That the decrease of the Weiss magneton value for the cobalt salts in alcoholic and HCl solutions cannot be explained on the production of anhydrous or dihydrate CoCl_2 is further proved by the observation of Foex (*loc. cit.*) that the value of p for cobalt chloride in concentrated sulphuric acid is 25.66 and not between 22 and 23 as it should have been if the simple hydration theory were true.